

Response of Upland Rice to Different Organic Nutrient Sources and Their Effect on Insect Population

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted in Randomized Complete Block Design with four replication and seven treatments to know the "Response of Upland Rice to Different Source of Organic Manures and their effect on insect population" at the agronomy farm of the Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science (IAAS), Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal using a variety "IR-55435-5" during rainy season, 2009. The treatments included are: farmyard manure (14 t ha⁻¹), decomposed biogas effluent (9 t ha⁻¹), fresh biogas effluent (8 t ha⁻¹), banmara compost (6 t ha⁻¹), ashok dry leaves compost (11 t ha⁻¹), rice husk compost (15 t ha⁻¹), and chemical fertilizer (NPK @ 100:60:40 kg ha⁻¹). The yield attributing factors of upland rice such as, effective tillers per meter square (192.3), panicle length (23.46cm), panicle weight (2.72 g), and grains per panicle (105.2) were significantly higher in chemical fertilizer applied plots than the rest of the sources of nutrient and those of the lowest (146.3 effective tillers, 21.01cm panicle length, 1.777 g panicle weight, and 68.06 grains per panicle) were in ashok dry leaves compost applied plots. The significantly ($p=0.05$) higher grain and straw yield (2.337 t ha⁻¹ grain and 7.708 t ha⁻¹) in chemical fertilizer applied plots were statistically at par with fresh biogas effluent (2.189 t ha⁻¹) and decomposed biogas effluent (2.050 t ha⁻¹). Harvest index (HI) of 32.53 %, 30.51 %, 29.55 %, 28.02 %, 26.72, 26.34 %, and 23.43 % were in decomposed biogas effluent, rice husk compost, fresh biogas effluent, ashok dry leaves compost, banmara compost, farmyard manure and chemical fertilizer were respectively. Significantly higher harvest index was observed in decomposed biogas effluent (32.53 %) applied plots than the chemical fertilizer applied plots (23.43 %) that was statistically at par with rest of the sources of nutrient. Result also revealed that beneficial insect's population was higher and harmful insect's population was lower in organic nutrient source treated plots. Thus, it was concluded that biogas effluent is the best source of nutrient among the organic manures and sound alternative to inorganic fertilizer.

Key words: Biogas-effluent, Inset-Population, IR-55435-5, Upland-Rice, Yield

1. Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most important food crops of the world (Singh and Khush, 2000). About 70 % of world's poor people are living in Asia and consuming around 92 % of the world's rice (IRRI, 2004). In Asia, rice is grown in 135 million ha with an annual production of 516 million t (Roy and Misra, 2002). In Nepal, rice occupies 1362908 hectares of land with a total production of 4299078 t and a productivity of 2.32 t ha⁻¹ (MoAC, 2017). Share of rice in the agricultural gross domestic product (AGDP) is 20 % and it contributes nearly 50 % to the total calorie requirement of Nepalese people (NARC, 2007). There are two distinct types of rice are being grown in Nepal: upland rice and low land rice.

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Upland rice (*Ghaiya Dhan* in Nepali) refers to rice grown on both flat and sloping fields that are not banded, and field is prepared and seeds are seeded under dry conditions, and that depends on rainfall for moisture (De Datta, 1975). At least 9 % (about 12,000 ha) of the total rice area in Nepal is under such condition (NARC, 2004). Upland rice is a crop of socially and economically disadvantaged ethnic communities like *Darai*, *Kumal*, and *Bote*, however, it is also grown by *Bramin*, *Chhetri*, and occupational castes living in areas dominated by *Tar* (semi-flat lands in the hills) (Joshi *et al.*, 2001).

Upland rice is commonly perceived to be a low-yielding crop grown by resource-poor farmers in the highlands. In Asia, upland rice yields average only about 1 t ha⁻¹ vs. 4.9 t ha⁻¹ of irrigated lowland rice (IRRI, 1997). The low yield of upland rice is because of its production being limited to low harvest index varieties; infertile soils and heavy weed infestation; increased cropping intensity; insufficient and irregular rainfall; and lack of improved production technologies and associated high yielding cultivars (George, 2001). Since upland rice is grown mostly by the resource poor farmers without an access to the modern inputs (chemical fertilizers), emphasis should be given to increase the production of this crop by the use of organic manures. Rather, the adoption of organic farming using locally available sources for crop nutrient management seems imperative.

Organic farming has been described as a complex system (Brumfield *et al.*, 2000) of agricultural production where productivity improves with increasing years (Lockeretz *et al.*, 1981). Several experimental transition studies have reported initially lower yields in organic farming, followed by yields similar to conventional (chemical based) production (MacRae *et al.*, 1990). Other materials such as *banmara* (*Eupatorium odoratum*) weeds and dry leaves of other common trees like *ashok* (*Polyalthia longifolia*) can also be used for preparing compost and application of such compost improves the crop performance and soil properties. Banmara is a common weed of waste and marginal pasturelands in Nepal. The luxuriant vegetative growth of this weed coupled with the spreading root systems extract large quantities of nutrients from the soil, and may act as a nutrient pump (Obatolu and Agboola, 1993). These materials are locally available, easy to use, cheap, and compatible farmer's practice and with long term sustainability and eco-friendly. This fact illustrates the need of research on the response of the crops to locally available materials, enriched by composting with biogas effluent as the source of nutrient supplement. To address the issue of using various organic manures (biogas effluent and its compost with other organic materials) in upland rice, a research was designed with the following objectives.

- To evaluate the response of upland rice to biogas based organic manures *vis-à-vis* farm yard manure and chemical fertilizers
- To assess the effect of different organic manures on insect population in rice field.

2. Materials and Methods

The soil of experimental site was sandy loam in texture with pH 5.93. The soil was low in organic matter content (1.8737 %), total nitrogen (0.0937 %), available phosphorus (12.061 kg ha⁻¹) and available potassium (24.8376 kg ha⁻¹) content. In order to evaluate the response of upland rice to different source of organic manures and their effect on insect population, a research was conducted in the agronomy farm of IAAS. The experiment was conducted in the research block of agronomy farm of Institute of Agriculture and Animal Science (IAAS) Rampur, Chitwan from April to November, 2009. This site is 256 meter above mean sea level at 27° 37' North latitude and 84° 25' East longitudes and was 9.8 km south-west from Bharatpur, headquarter of Chitwan district (Thapa and Dangol, 1988). The experimental site was in sub-humid subtropical climatic condition with cool winters, hot summers and distinct rainy season with annual rainfall of about 1919.5 mm (NMRP, 2000). The total rainfall of 1909.30 mm was received during the entire period of experimentation from April-9 to December-9. The highest rainfall was recorded during July (753.5 mm) and no rainfall in a month of November (0 mm). The rice crop was seeded dated on June-27. The relative humidity ranged from 57.5 % in the month of April to 98.8 % in the month of December. The mean maximum temperature during the experimental period ranged from 23.4°C to 37.41°C. It was the highest during April and the lowest during December. The mean minimum temperature during cropping period ranged from 10.2°C to 26.5°C. It was the highest during July and the lowest during December.

2.1. Materials

Organic manures: Six different types of organic manures locally prepared, using locally available materials in the IAAS farm, were used in upland rice to supply the nitrogen equivalent to 100 kg N ha⁻¹. **Chemical fertilizers:** Urea, DAP and mutate of potash available in the market, were used to evaluate comparative effects of organic manures and chemical fertilizers. **Upland rice variety:** Upland rice variety used in the experiment was IR-55435-5.

2.2. Preparation of Compost

Different types of compost namely; banmara compost, ashok dry leaves compost, and rice husk compost were prepared by mixing locally available materials with biogas effluent. The compost was prepared by pit method. Pits size of 1 m x 0.75 m x 0.5m were dug near the experimental field. After digging the pit, biogas effluent and composting material (1:1 ratio) were mixed layer wise. The compost was left in the pit for two and half months to allow complete decomposition. The turning of compost was done two times during decomposition process. The followings were the different types of compost.

Banmara compost: Banmara compost was prepared by mixing 1 part of biogas effluent with 1 part of banmara (Biogas effluent + banmara) on weight basis.

Ashok (*Polyalthia longifolia*) dry leaves compost: The compost prepared by mixing 1 part of biogas effluent with 1 part of ashok dry leaves (Biogas effluent + ashok dry leaves) in a compost pit.

Rice husk compost: Mixing 1 part of biogas effluent with 1 part of rice husk (Biogas effluent + rice husk), rice husk compost was prepared.

Farmyard manure (FYM): It prepared by the farmers on their traditional way, heap method, was used as one of the sources of nutrient.

Biogas effluent: Biogas effluent was collected from the farmers having biogas plant.

2.3. Analysis of Manures

Three samples of compost were taken from top, medium, and lower layers and was made a composite sample then analyzed on the dry weight basis.

Table 5: Nutrient contents of different types of compost used in the research at IAAS, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal

S.N.	Description	N%	P%	K%
1	Farmyard manure	0.71	0.35	0.99
2	Decomposed biogas effluent	1.11	0.22	0.35
3	Fresh biogas effluent	1.20	0.40	0.65
4	Banmara compost	1.71	0.42	0.65
5	Ashok dry leaves compost	0.93	0.31	0.60
6	Rice husk compost	0.66	0.21	0.35

2.4. Field Layout for the Experiment

The experimental field was laid out in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications and seven treatments with plot size of 12 m² (4 m x 3 m). There was a bund of 0.5 m width between two experimental plots and each replication was separated by bund of 1 m width. There were 15 rows of 3 m length in each plot with crop geometry 25 cm between rows and seeded continuously.

2.5. Treatments Details and Symbols

Seven different sources of plant nutrients including chemical fertilizers was used as nutrient sources for nutrition of upland rice. The quantity of manure was applied to supply 100 kg N ha⁻¹.

Table 6: Details of the treatments for upland rice experiments at IAAS, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal,

S. N.	Treatments Combination	Symbol
1	Farmyard manure (FYM) @ 14 t ha ⁻¹	T ₁
2	Decomposed biogas effluent @ 9 t ha ⁻¹	T ₂
3	Fresh biogas effluent @ 8 t ha ⁻¹	T ₃
4	Banmara compost (Compost of 1 part biogas effluent + 1 part banmara) @ 6 t ha ⁻¹	T ₄
5	Ashok dry leaves compost (Compost of 1 part biogas effluent + 1 part ashok dry leaves) @ 11 t ha ⁻¹	T ₅
6	Rice husk compost (Compost of 1 part biogas effluent + 1 part rice husk) @ 15 t ha ⁻¹	T ₆
7	Chemical fertilizer (NPK @ 100:60:40 kg ha ⁻¹)	T ₇

2.6. Cultivation Practices

Twenty eight plots were prepared according to the experimental design. The spacing between rows was maintained at 25 cm and seed rate was 80 kg ha⁻¹. Different sources of plant nutrients including both organic and inorganic manures were applied @ 100 kg N ha⁻¹ in the field. Nitrogen, phosphorus and potash was applied as recommended @ 100:60:40 kg NPK ha⁻¹ through urea (46 % N), DAP (18 % N and 46 % P₂O₅) and MOP (60 % K₂O). Half dose of Nitrogen and full dose of phosphorus and potash (50:60:40 kg NPK ha⁻¹) were applied before final land preparation as basal dose treatments. Remaining half dose of N was applied in two split doses at active tailoring stage and panicle initiation. The amount of different organic composts used on the experiment was given below and they were recommended by the actual nutrient calculation. Two weeding operations were performed at 25 and 45 days after seeding (DAS). No chemicals were used to control insects and disease. The crop from the net plot area (1 meter square) was harvested manually with the help of sickles. Threshing was done manually and grains were cleaned by winnowing and weighted.

2.7. Observation Recorded in Upland Rice

Number of leaves was counted from the destructive samples taken from an area of 250 cm² (10 cm x 25 cm) at 15 days interval from 45th days after seeding the experiment. Leaf area (cm²) of the functional leaves obtained at 15 day interval starting from 45th DAS from the sample of area of 250 cm² (10 cm x 25 cm) which was selected randomly for growth analysis i.e. drawn for dry matter accumulation study. The leaf area was measured by Automated Leaf Area Meter. The leaf area so obtained was then used to calculate the leaf area index.

Leaf area index (LAI) = Leaf area/ground area

2.8. Growth Analysis

Plant samples were taken from the area of 250 cm² (25cm x 10 cm), considered as destructing sampling area, from each plot at an interval of 15 days from 45th days after seeding till the flowering. Plant from this area was taken by digging to the depth of 25 cm from a distance of 10

cm from all sides. Thereafter total dry weight of plant samples of leaves, stems, roots and panicles was measured. Dry matter deposition was determined by drying plant organs at a temperature of 70°C in hot oven till constant weight (48 hours).

Number of Effective Tillers Per Meter Square

The number of effective tillers per meter square was counted from each plot just before harvesting of the crop.

Length and Weight of Panicle

The length (cm) and weight (g) of panicle were taken from the 20 randomly selected panicles from net plot just before harvesting and mean was calculated.

Number and Weight of Grains Per Panicle

The filled and unfilled grains from randomly selected 20 panicles from the net plot were counted and weighed in electronic balance.

Thousand Grain Weight (Test Grain Weight)

Thousand grains from the yield lot, at 12 % moisture content, of net plot harvest were counted and weighed using Portable Automatic Electronic Balance and expressed in gram (g).

Grain Yield (kg ha⁻¹)

After threshing, the grain and straw of individual plot were separated. The moisture of the grain was taken by portable moisture meter for each individual plot. The grain yields of net plot were adjusted at 12 % moisture level and calculated with the help of following formula.

$$\text{Grain yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{) at 12 \% moisture} = (100 - \text{MC}) \times \text{Plot yield (kg)} \times 10000 \text{ (m}^2\text{)} \\ (100 - 12) \times \text{net plot area (m}^2\text{)}$$

Where, MC is the moisture content in percentage of the grains.

Grain yield from net plot of 1 m² was measured for all the treatments and plots and mean was calculated.

Straw Yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Straw yield (kg ha⁻¹) was also measured from the rows of net plot area and then translated into hectare.

Harvest Index

Harvest index (HI) was computed by dividing grain yield with the total straw yield as per the following formula.

$$\text{HI\%} = (\text{grain yield} \times 100) / (\text{grain yield} + \text{straw yield})$$

2.9. Effect of Treatment on Insect Population

The effect of treatments on both beneficial and harmful insects was studied at different growth stages of rice crop. Number of tiger beetles present in each sample plant was recorded by visual observation. For spiders, their number present in each sample rice hill was noted using same method. In case of Brown Plant Hopper (BPH) and leaf hoppers, their presence in each tiller of sample hill was recorded with close observation of sample plant by not disturbing them. Number of stem borers present in per square feet area was recorded.

2.10. Statistical Analysis

All the recorded data were subjected to analysis of variance and Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used for mean separations as per Gomez and Gomez (1984). Microsoft word 2003 was used for word processing, MS excels for tables, graphs, and simple statistical analysis and, MSTAT-C Microsoft computer programs were used for running statistical analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

The outcomes of the experiment conducted in Rampur, Chitwan with the objective to evaluate different organic manures for upland rice nutrition are presented in this chapter.

3.1. Number of Effective Tillers Per Meter Square

The average number of effective tiller per meter square of upland rice was 166.614 and ranged from 140.8 to 192.3. Significantly ($p=0.05$) higher number of effective tillers (192.3) per meter square was observed in chemical fertilizer applied plots and it was statistically at par with fresh biogas effluent (186.8) and decomposed biogas effluent (180.9) applied plots. The number of effective tillers per meter square in rice husk compost (159.8) and banmara compost applied plot (159.4) was comparable and were significantly higher than farmyard manure compost and ashok dry leaves compost applied plot. The minimum number of tillers (140.8) was observed in farmyard manure and was statistically at par with ashok dry leaves compost (146.3) applied plot (Table 3).

3.2. Panicle Length

The panicle length of upland rice was varied from 21.01 cm to 23.46 cm. The significantly ($p=0.05$) longer panicle length (23.46 cm) was obtained from the chemical fertilizer applied plots than other nutrient sources whereas panicle length among the rest of the nutrient sources were comparable. The shorter panicle length (21.01) was observed in ashok dry leaves compost applied plots (Fig. 1).

3.3. Panicle Weight

The analysis of data showed that the average weight of panicles of upland rice in the experiment was 2.19 g and was varied from 1.777 g to 2.720 g. The panicle weight (2.720 g) was significantly ($p=0.05$) higher in chemical fertilizer applied plot and was statistically at par with the decomposed biogas effluent applied plots (2.345 g). The ashok dry leaves compost applied plot produced the lowest (1.777 g) panicle weight and was statistically at par with the application of banmara compost (2.035 g), farmyard manure (2.112 g), rice husk compost (2.169 g) and fresh biogas effluent (2.174 g) (Fig. 1).

3.4. Grains Per Panicle

The average number of grains per panicle of upland rice was 81.615 and it ranged from 68.06 to 105.2. The grain per panicle (105.2) was observed significantly ($p=0.05$) higher in chemical fertilizer applied plots followed by the fresh biogas effluent (89.07). The lowest grain per panicle (68.06) was observed in ashok dry leaves compost applied plots and was statistically at par with the application of farmyard manure (74.28). The grain per panicle in banmara compost

(79.50), decomposed biogas effluent (78.25), rice husk compost (76.75) and farmyard manure (74.28) applied plots were comparable (Fig. 1).

Application of chemical fertilizer significantly increased the yield attributes such as panicle length, panicle weight and grains per panicle. This trend might be due to role of nitrogen in crop maturation, flowering and fruiting including seed formation. These results are in accordance with those of (Ahmad, 1989). The highest panicles length, weight and grains per panicle of rice were recorded when nitrogen was supplied in 100 % through inorganic form (Brahmanand, 2009).

3.5. Thousand Grain Weight (TGW)

The average thousand grain weight of upland rice was 25.18 g. There was no significant ($p=0.05$) difference among the treatments for thousand grain weight. The highest thousand grain weight (25.87 g) was obtained from the chemical fertilizer applied plots followed by the decomposed biogas effluent (25.63 g), fresh biogas effluent (25.33 g) and farmyard manure (25.31 g). The lowest thousand grain weight (24.29 g) was obtained from ashok dry leaves compost applied plots (Fig. 1).

Higher recovery efficiency and more N available to the crop which increase in grain weight due to increase in chlorophyll concentration in leaves which led to higher photosynthetic rate and ultimately plenty of photosynthates available during grain development might be a cause of higher thousand grain yield in chemical fertilizer applied plots. Bhujel *et al.* (1997) observed similar results by applying recommended dose of N (100 kg N ha⁻¹) and 10 t ha⁻¹ of FYM. Dwivedi and Thakur (2000) reported that the thousand grain weight was not influenced significantly due to different inorganic, organic and integrated fertility management practices.

Figure 1: Yield attributing factors of upland rice variety IR 55435-5 under application of different sources of nutrient, field experiment at IAAS, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal

3.6. Grain Yield

The grain yield (Table 3) of upland rice ranged from 1.634 t ha⁻¹ to 2.337 t ha⁻¹ and the average grain yield in the experiment was 1.89 t ha⁻¹. The chemical fertilizer applied plots produce significantly ($p= 0.05$) higher grain yield (2.337 t ha⁻¹) and was statistically at par with that of fresh biogas effluent (2.189 t ha⁻¹) and decomposed biogas effluent (2.050 t ha⁻¹) applied plots. The lowest grain yield (1.634 t ha⁻¹) was produced from ashok dry leaves compost applied plots and was statistically at par with the grain yield of rest of the nutrient sources except with chemical fertilizer and fresh biogas effluent applied plots (Table 3).

3.7. Straw Yield

The straw yield (Table 3) of upland rice ranged from 3.936 t ha⁻¹ to 7.708 t ha⁻¹ and the average straw yield was observed as 4.935 t ha⁻¹. The straw yield (7.707 t ha⁻¹) was significantly ($p= 0.05$) higher in chemical fertilizer applied plots, whereas the lowest (3.936 t ha⁻¹) of that was obtained from the rice husk compost applied plots (Table 3). The straw yield obtained from organic sources of nutrient were non significant.

3.8. Harvest Index (HI)

Harvest index (HI) of upland rice under the application of decomposed biogas effluent, rice husk compost, fresh biogas effluent, ashok dry leaves compost, banmara compost, farmyard manure and chemical fertilizer were (32.53 %), (30.51 %), (29.55 %), (28.02 %), (26.72), (26.34 %), and (23.43 %), respectively. Among them, significantly ($p= 0.05$) higher harvest index (32.53 %) was obtained from decomposed biogas effluent applied plots than the chemical fertilizer applied plots (23.43 %) but that was at par with the rice husk compost (30.51 %), fresh biogas effluent (29.55 %), ashok dry leaves compost (28.02 %), banmara compost (26.72) and farmyard manure (26.34 %) applied plots (Table 3).

Higher grain yield and straw yield of upland rice in chemical fertilizer could be because of the nutrient elements in the mineral fertilizer were in the readily available form, whereas more time could be taken in mineralization of organic manure. The grain and straw yield of rice was higher in chemical fertilizer applied treatments and that was statistically at par with fresh and decomposed biogas effluent applied treatments. It was supported by Fulford (1978) and Acharya (1961). The higher yield with fresh biogas effluent was attributed to contain higher percent of mineral nitrogen (1.6 %) and was readily available than the decomposed effluent (less than 0.5 %) (Karki,1997). Decomposed effluent had narrower C:N ratio as compared to farm yard manure, ashok dry leaves compost and rice husk so that the former gave better crop yield than the latter (Schulz, 1990).

Table 7: Effect of different sources of nutrient on yield of upland rice, field experiment at IAAS, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal

Treatments	Effective tillers	Grain Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest Index (%)
Farmyard manure	140.8 ^c	1.675 ^{bc}	4.611 ^b	26.34 ^{ab}
Decomposed biogas effluent	180.9 ^a	2.050 ^{abc}	4.597 ^b	32.53 ^a
Fresh biogas effluent	186.8 ^a	2.189 ^{ab}	4.916 ^b	29.55 ^{ab}
Banmara compost	159.4 ^b	1.670 ^{bc}	4.571 ^b	26.72 ^{ab}
Ashok dry leaves compost	146.3 ^c	1.634 ^c	4.141 ^b	28.02 ^{ab}
Rice husk compost	159.8 ^b	1.718 ^{bc}	3.936 ^b	30.51 ^a
Chemical fertilizer	192.3 ^a	2.337 ^a	7.708 ^a	23.43 ^b
SEM±	3.969	0.1651	0.3260	2.109
LSD _{0.05}	11.79	0.4905	0.9685	6.267
CV%	4.76	17.44	13.23	14.98

Treatments means followed by common letter (s) within column are not significantly different among the treatments (DMRT at 5% level of significance)

3.9. Effect on Insect Population

Average population of tiger beetles were under decomposed biogas effluent, rice husk compost, farmyard manure, fresh biogas effluent, ashok dry leaves compost and chemical fertilizer were (8.33), (5.33), (5.00), (4.67), (4.67), (4.33) and (1.00), respectively. Among various treatment, highest number of spider was observed (10.67) in decomposed biogas effluent which was followed farmyard manure (9.33), fresh biogas effluent (8.00), banmara compost (7.33), ashok dry leaves compost (7.00), rice husk compost (6.00) and chemical fertilizer (2.00). Population of BPH was found to be statistically ($p=0.05$) higher in chemical fertilizer treated plot than rest of all treated plots (Table:4). Similarly the population of leaf hoppers was statistically higher ($p=0.05$) than all other treated plots. In the same way, population of stem borers showed the similar pattern as BPH and leaf hopper followed. It was supported by Chau and Heong (2005) where they observed that the highest number of harmful insect population (BPH, Leaf hoppers, stem borers) were found higher in inorganic fertilizer treated plot as compared to organic resource treated plots. Likewise, this result was supported by Altieri and Nicolls (2003).

Table 4: Effect of different sources of nutrient on insect population in upland rice field experiment at IAAS, Rampur, Chitwan, Nepal

Treatments	Tiger beetle/hill	Spiders/hill	BPH/tiller	Leaf hoppers/tiller	Stem borers /sq feet
Farmyard manure	5.00 ^b	9.33 ^a	2.66 ^c	4.00 ^b	2.00 ^b
Decomposed biogas effluent	8.33 ^a	10.67 ^a	2.66 ^c	4.00 ^b	2.33 ^b
Fresh biogas effluent	4.67 ^b	8.00 ^{bc}	4.00 ^b	3.66 ^b	1.66 ^b
Banmara compost	4.33 ^b	7.33 ^{bc}	3.66 ^{bc}	4.33 ^b	1.66 ^b
Ashok dry leave compost	4.67 ^b	7.00 ^{bc}	3.00 ^{bc}	3.33 ^b	1.66 ^b
Rice husk compost	5.33 ^b	6.00 ^c	2.66 ^c	3.66 ^b	1.33 ^b
Chemical fertilizer	1.00 ^c	2.00 ^d	9.33 ^a	14.33 ^a	7.00 ^a
SEM±	0.34	1.56	0.39	0.81	0.43
LSD _{0.05}	1.03	2.22	1.12	1.60	1.17
CV%	12.26	17.38	15.74	16.95	16.17

Treatments means followed by common letter (s) within column are not significantly different among the treatments (DMRT at 5% level of significance)

3.10. Conclusion

On the basis of the result obtained from a season experiment it is concluded that biogas effluent is the best source of nutrient among the organic manures and sound alternative to inorganic fertilizer. Further experimentation on the issue for further verification of the information obtained so far is suggested.

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